

International Workshop

"Technologies Nexus Intelligence Society"

Hybrid – online & in-person
 July 26, 2024, Oxford, UNITED KINGDOM

Registration of the participants	08.00-08.30
Event welcome	08.30-08.45
Plenary speakers	08.45-11.00
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i>	08.45-09.15
<i>Technologies: Navigating the Future of Society through Data-Driven Systems and the Dynamics of Digital Transformation</i>	09.15-10.45
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i>	
<i>Intelligence: Shaping the Future of Society through Interconnected Innovation</i>	
Q & A	10.45-11.00
Parallel sessions	11.00-12.00
<i>Session 1 – Intelligent Technologies and Society's Future</i>	
<i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i>	11.00-11.30
<i>Intelligent Technologies and Society's Future: Exploring the Impact of AI, Automation, and Data on Social Structures and Global Progress</i>	
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i>	11.30-12.00
<i>Intelligent Technologies and Society's Future: Analyzing the Transformative Effects of AI, Automation, and Data on Social Systems, Economic Structures, and Global Development</i>	
<i>Session 2 – Society in the Age of Intelligence</i>	

<p><i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences</i></p> <p><i>Austria</i></p> <p><i>Society in the Age of Intelligence: Navigating the Impacts of Artificial Intelligence, Data, and Automation on Social Dynamics, Ethics, and Global Progress</i></p>	11.00-11.30
<p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandina Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Society in the Age of Intelligence: Understanding the Intersection of AI, Automation, and Data in Shaping Social Structures, Ethical Challenges, and Global Advancement</i></p>	11.30-12.00
<p>Coffee break</p>	12.00-12.15
<p><i>Session 1 – Intelligent Technologies and Society's Future</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Intelligent Technologies and Society's Future: Examining the Role of AI, Machine Learning, and Automation in Shaping Social Systems, Economic Models, and Ethical Frameworks</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Intelligent Technologies and Society's Future: Exploring the Transformation of Social Norms, Economic Systems, and Governance in the Era of AI and Automation</i></p>	12.45-13.15
<p><i>Session 2 – Society in the Age of Intelligence</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Society in the Age of Intelligence: Exploring the Transformative Impact of Artificial Intelligence, Data Science, and Automation on Social Structures, Culture, and Global Governance</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Society in the Age of Intelligence: Investigating the Far-reaching Effects of Artificial Intelligence, Data Science, and Automation on Social Dynamics, Cultural Evolution, and Global Governance Frameworks</i></p>	12.45-13.15
<p>Q&A</p>	13.15-13.45

CBM International University USA
Akademos Learning UK
9462-9755 Quebec CA & AT (Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences)

Concluding remarks	13.45-14.00
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Location: Oxford Science, John Eccles House, Oxford, OX4 4GP, United Kingdom